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ROLL OF MOTIVATIONAL THEORIES CHILDREN'S LEARNING MOTIVATING CHILDREN OF LEARN

Dr. USHA GODARA

Lecturer of J.B.T.T. INSTITUTE

23 PTP Sadul shahar

Sri Gangangar (Raj.)

Abstract

It is a common experience that not all student in a class display similarity of interest in learning. Some may show more interest, say in sports, While some others may be interested in social activities. It is also a possible that a girl had extraordinary fair for language learning. Ordinary A boy might as well have excelled in mathematics achievement. All these manifested pattern. Psychologists call them need for power, social, and achievement motivation. They are inferences about motivated behaviors of the students, what person does to achieve her/his desired goal. It is then, obvious from these observation that fundamentally all behavior is goal directed, whether It he humans and/or sub-human species. The concept of motivation like any other psychological construct has evolved over a period of time, on the basis of better understanding of how human/ animal behavior develops. Different theories of motivation provide us with an explanation for the occurrence of motivated behavior among the humans and animals.

This unit is written with a purpose of understanding the concept nature and theories of motivation. More emphasis however, is placed on how to motivated children so that they start learning on their own.

Key words: Motivating theory, learning, children.

Learning outcomes

After studying this meter, you should be able to,

- Analyses the different theories of motivation,
- Illustrate with examples the meaning of each theory,
- Improve your students motivation to learn through learning strategies,
- Explain how each theory contributes in motivating children to learn,
- Analyses the concept of achievement motivation and its significance in teaching .

What is motivation o learn ?

You must have observed that different students have different levels of motivation of learn different subjects of curriculum. Some are interested in science or mathematics, others

prefer to study social science or humanities, and still others are motivated to perform in athletics or in art.

Some students may be studying a particular subject, but that may not really be liking that. Kamlesh, for example, is studying science exam though she dislikes science. She is admitted to the course only for the reason that passing 10+2 examination with science would enable her to seek examination in a technical course.

Pratibha on the other hand likes science. She wants to understand every concept and show it is usable. She understands the importance of science for her future career besides, being really motivated to learn she finds reading science a fun and quite interesting.

Kamlesh's motivation to learn is just to pass the examination to become eligible somehow but Pratibha is really motivated to learn. Motivation to learner is the tendency to find related activities meaningful and work while. It is also trying to get maximum benefit from them.

Those who are motivated to learn emphasize learning goals more than performance goals, they are concerned with acquiring skills, knowledge and understanding related with field of study. But those are students who emphasize performance goals. They want to show that they are good, they want to loaf are interested simply in showing performance to impress people.

- Biological theories of motivation

Instinct on the basis of Darwin's work on emotions, it was asserted that animals and humans share instincts alike in modeling their manifested behaviors. William McDougall (1908) proposed that all our thoughts and behaviors are the cause of inherited instincts. Freudian psychoanalytic theory also attributes human behavior to innate forces. He opined that two basic urges govern our behaviors.

The life instincts and the death instincts the former ones are shaped into several behaviors the latter encompass the aggressive acts. The instincts through the unconscious form powerful motivational forces in shaping human behaviors.

- Need and drive

Around 1920 the instinctive theory was modified in favor of drive conception of motivated behavior. An organism experiences an aroused state on the basis of biological needs like food, thirst and sex. This arousal condition is called a drive. It motivates the organism to reduce the need.

- Opponent process theory

This theory takes a hedonistic view of motivated behaviors. There what is pleasant and what is unpleasant of the organism forms the basis for motivated behavior.

- Optimal level theory

This theory is also another shade of hedonism as a source of motivated behavior. Here a certain optimal level of arousal elicits pleasure. The individual is motivated to behave in such a way as to maintain the optimal level of arousal, this concept is close to homeostasis that is emphasized by biological motivation (need drive reduction).

Cognitive and others theories of motivation assert that occurrence of human behavior cannot be attributed to have originated on the principle of pleasure pain exclusively.

- Psychological theories of motivation

Incentive theory

Incentives and drive are internal condition of the organism. Then on the basis of overtly manifested behaviors. Ghstincts needs, drive, and psychoanalytic theories of motivation, therefore follow biological approach. During 1950s psychologists started looking for explanations of motivation on the basis of external stimuli that motivate individuals/ animals behaviors are called incentives.

- Focus on learning strategies

We know now that cognitive approaches to learning place as much emphasis on the processes of learning as on the outcomes. This is also true of the cognitive Approaches to motivation. Attribution theory in particular stresses that teachers point out what learner's are doing during the processes of learning and not just what they have accomplished.

Achievement motivation (n-achievement) much of the human behaviors is larut because of the socialization processes In me Cleland's it al (1971) view, school learning is affected by the need achievement need for affiliation and need for power which are define as under.

- Achievement to accomplish difficult tasks to rival and surpass authors.
- Affiliation to sec and enjoy cooperation with others to make friends and.
- Dominance to control and influence the behavior of others to be a lager.
High n-achievers display
- Working on moderately challenging tasks because it increases promise of success ,
- They make good match between their abilities and task demands,
- They like comparison of task performance with that of others and prefer feedback on how they hover performed and.
- After success on a ask they raise their level of aspiration to do new difficult tasks better.

N-power motivation

This motive has been expressed in different ways. It has been defined as the ability or capacity of a person to produce or intended effects on the behavior or emotion of another persons.

Stimulus and exploratory needs

These needs are based on the curiosity motive about things and their explorations. Monkeys have displayed these behaviors very well. Human beings as well are stimulation seekers. According to beryline(1971) environmental stimuli arouse all of us. A novel, complete stimulus motivation.

Effectance motivation (is much more than the other ones) with (1959) calls it a general motive to act competently and interacting with the environment. Effectance plays an important role in human motivation. It has been argued, even it a goal is achieved by a person, the effectance motivation remains viable and vibrant enough to maintain new competencies.

Cognitive theorie :- the cognitive basis of learning emphasizes importance of mental processes for maintaining and monitoring our motivational states because they help in goal directed behaviors.

Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation :- intrinsic motivation is somewhat akin to effectance motivation. It has been defined as a persons need for ceiling competent and self – determining in dealing with the environment it is called intrinsic, because, the goals are internal feelings of effectiveness competence and self determination.

Self actualization motivation

Our of the most ambitious attempts to explain motivation was abraham masseuse.

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